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Empower teachers for
remote online assessments
in higher education

Evaluation Study of Stakeholder Perspectives on Online Assessment

**Supplementary material IO2:
Questionnaires' templates**

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Introduction

As part of the second intellectual output (IO2), we developed three different surveys to explore the perceptions of instructors, students and administrators (stakeholders) about online assessment within the partner institutions.

In this report of supplementary material, we make the three surveys in English publicly available, being published with a license that allows any researcher to reuse the materials, adapt them and share them with the same kind of license. Spanish and German versions are also available on request.

As an important note, we would like to acknowledge that the questionnaires are not validated.

To know more about the development process of the surveys, please consult the [Report on IO2](#).

List of surveys:

- [Instructors' survey](#), pages 4-9.
- [Students' survey](#), pages 10-14.
- [Administrators' survey](#), pages 15-19.

Instructors' "Survey on Online Assessment in Higher Education"

The Remote.EDU Project (2020-1-DE01-KA226-HE-005782) aims to explore the perceptions of instructors, students and administrators (stakeholders) about online assessment in higher education institutions. The results of this study will serve to draw on the current situation in each of the institutions to consider local, institutional and national perspectives, and will inform the design of concepts for online assessment, the needs for online assessment for virtual mobility and the development of a professional development course for online assessment.

We understand *online assessment, e-assessment or electronic assessment* as a teaching strategy to use technology to assess and evaluate learning goals and acquired competencies, in **any educational modality** (in-class, blended or hybrid learning, online learning) and **moment in the process** (formative e-assessment or assessment for learning during the course of instruction, and summative e-assessment at the end of a course or teaching unit that includes scoring or grading). In addition, we consider *online assessment in an international context* the situation where students are studying remotely at an institution in another country and therefore also need to be evaluated remotely.

In this survey, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions about online assessment based on **your perceptions as instructor**. Estimated time to answer is 15 minutes.

The survey is structured with 25 questions in 4 parts:

Part A: Factors associated with the use of online assessment

Part B: Attitudes, practices and preferences of online assessment methods

Part C: Contextual and institutional factors

Part D: Profile as instructor

The survey is completely anonymous, because in no case will identifying data of the participants be collected (names, email addresses or IP addresses of mobile devices), nor will it be possible to deduce the identity of the participants from their answers in the survey.

We greatly appreciate your feedback to design concepts for online assessment and create a course for supporting your professional development on this topic.

If you have any questions about the project or participation in the survey, please send them to [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].

Part A: Factors associated with the use of online assessment

1. How familiar are you with the implementation of online assessment practices?
(rating scale ranging from 1 to 5; 1 not at all -I have never applied online assessment, 5 - completely, I have gained some experience in online assessment practices).
2. Did you have some experience with online assessment before COVID-19?
Yes/No
 - a) Is this experience in an online postgraduate or degree? Yes/No.
 - b) Explain more. Open textbox.
3. How prepared are you for online assessment practices?
(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-not at all, 5-very well prepared).
 - a) In terms of assessment competences? (e.g., knowledge and use of strategies for assessment)
 - b) In terms of pedagogical competences? (e.g., knowledge and abilities to align teaching and assessment)
 - c) In terms of digital competences? (e.g., knowledge and use of digital tools for assessment)
 - d) In terms of cultural competences? (e.g., how to assess in groups culturally diverse, e.g., with international students)
4. Have you attended any professional development course on online assessment?
Yes/No
 - a) If yes, about what specific topic? (e.g., tools, strategies, etc.) Open textbox.
5. When I discuss the information about the online assessment(s) of my course to my students do I...?
(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3- sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)
 - a) Explain the assessment formats of the course.
 - b) Explain the kind of assessment questions/criteria and grading.
 - c) Explain their rights as students concerning assessment.
 - d) Explain the procedure to review the assessment.
 - e) Give them enough time to prepare themselves for the adopted assessment formats.
 - f) Provide them support if having technical difficulties.

Part B: Attitudes, practices and preferences of online assessment

6. To what extent you agree with the following statements
(Likert scale 1-5): (rating scale ranging from 1 to 5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree)
 - a) Online assessment can be implemented in my courses without relevant issues.
 - b) Online assessment only applies for formative assessment (during the learning process).
Online assessment is easier to design compared to assessment in presence.
 - c) Online assessment takes less time to design than in presence assessment.

- d) Online assessment is easier to implement compared to assessment in presence.
- e) Online assessment facilitates the management of the assessment.
- f) Online assessment is less demanding for correction than in presence assessment.
- g) Online assessment is well received by students.
- h) Online assessment allows me to do a better monitoring and control of the learning process of my students than assessment in presence.
- i) Online assessment opens new opportunities of monitoring the learning process of my students.
- j) Online assessment facilitates originality and creativity.
- k) Online assessment offers more possibilities for personalized assessment than assessment in presence.
- l) Online assessment facilitates the situation of mobility students.
- m) Online assessment facilitates providing feedback to the students.
- n) Online assessment requires improved security systems to ensure authorship and detect plagiarism.
- o) Online assessment requires research for a greater consistency with an approach of competence-based assessment.
- p) Online assessment requires more research for improving practice.

7. Which types of online assessment practices...

(matrix with the practices to evaluate)

- a) do you know? (multiple choice)
- b) have you put into practice for formative assessment? (during the learning process)
(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3- sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)
- c) have you put into practice for summative assessment? (at the end of the learning process)
(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3- sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)
- d) do you feel more comfortable with? (multiple choice)

Closed-book written exam (written exam without supporting materials (notes, books))

Open-book written exam (written exam with supporting materials (notes, books))

Oral exam Quiz or tests (multiple choice, true/false, etc.)

Portfolio or e-portfolio

Papers/written assignments

Project Presentation (individual or group; poster, exhibitions)

Simulations

Case analysis

Self-assessment

Peer assessment

Others (specify)

8. With which online/digital tools did you realize them... ?

(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3-sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)

LMS task/assignment

LMS questionnaire

LMS forums

Other LMS tools

Videoconference system

Video recording spaces
Video repositories (e.g., Youtube)
Audio recording and repositories (podcast)
External questionnaires (e.g., Kahoot, Socrative)
Online work suites (e.g., Office Word, Google Docs)
Games and/or simulators
Website (e.g., Google Sites, Wix, etc.)
Blog (e.g., Wordpress, Blogger, etc.)
Wiki
Infographics (e.g., easel.ly, Canva)
Digital rubrics and/or checklists
Proctoring software
Safe exam browser
Plagiarism tools (e.g., Turnitin)
Other (specify)

Part C: Contextual and institutional factors

9. Do you recently or currently had/have administrative charges (e.g., vicedean, head of studies, etc.):

Yes/No

10. To which extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please rate from 1 to 5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree. If you do not know, please select "I do not know".

- Digital learning (and the possibility to do online assessment) is essential for the future of the institution.
- Digital learning and online assessment are part of the mission, vision and global strategy of the institution.
- There is a model of direction and governance regarding digital learning and online assessment.
- There are institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment.
- There are institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment in your faculty / study program(s).
- Learning analytics (data from the learning process and product) are considered strategically by the institution.

11. Do you think the institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment have been modified/removed/adapted since its development?

Yes/No

a) Please, explain (open textbox).

12. From your perspective, how does institutional assessment culture and policy influence online assessment practices? Open textbox.

13. Have you sought institutional support for online assessment practices?

Yes/No

a) If yes (checkboxes): Technical (e.g., how to use a specific tool)/Pedagogical, (e.g., how to create good assessment questions)/Legal (e.g., how to deal with the use of cameras in videoconferences)/Administrative (e.g., how to proceed with grading in the institutional system)/ Other

b) Did this support satisfy your need? (Yes/No). Why? Please, explain more about this support. Open textbox

c) How did this support take place? a) personal consultation; b) through a course; c) through resources created ad-hoc in the institutional spaces (e.g., videotutorials, infographics, ...);

d) informal support between peers,

e) Other, specify.

14. Have you sought support for online assessment practices on your own?

Yes/No

a) Please, explain (textbox).

15. Do you consider the infrastructure offered by the institution enough to design and implement online assessment? (e.g. tools offered, etc.)

Yes/No

a) Why (yes/not)? Please explain briefly (open textbox).

16. From your perspective, what are preconditions for online assessment to work regarding infrastructure, policies, administrative procedures, etc.?

Open textbox.

17. From your point of view, how did COVID-19 affect the design, implementation and support of online assessment?

Open textbox.

18. Which opportunities do you see for online assessment in international contexts?

Open textbox.

19. Which challenges do you use for online assessment in international context?

Open textbox.

Part D: Profile as instructor

20. Faculty:

List of faculties according to each university.

21. Discipline where you usually teach:

Health & Welfare / Natural Science, Maths & Statistics / Education / Arts & Humanities / Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction / Business, Administration & Law / Social Sciences, Journalism & Information / ICT / Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Veterinary / Other

22. Higher education level where you teach:

Bachelor/Master/Both

23. Teaching experience:

Numeric field.

24. Usual teaching workload in ECTs in an academic year:

Numeric field.

25. Approximate size of your classes (number of students)

Numeric field.

Comments, observations... (open text box, voluntary)

If you would like to add something else regarding the questionnaire or the study, please do it so here.

Thank you very much for your participation!

To conclude: if you have a good practice example of online assessment in an international context to share, please contact [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].

Students' "Survey on Online Assessment in Higher Education"

The Remote.EDU Project (2020-1-DE01-KA226-HE-005782) aims to explore the perceptions of instructors, students and administrators (stakeholders) about online assessment in higher education institutions. The results of this study will serve to draw on the current situation in each of the institutions to consider local, institutional and national perspectives, and will inform the design of concepts for online assessment, the needs for online assessment for virtual mobility and the development of a professional development course for online assessment.

We understand *online assessment, e-assessment or electronic assessment* as a teaching strategy to use technology to assess and evaluate learning goals and acquired competencies, **in any educational modality** (in-class, blended or hybrid learning, online learning) **and moment in the process** (formative e-assessment or assessment for learning during the course of instruction, and summative e-assessment at the end of a course or teaching unit that includes scoring or grading). In addition, we consider *online assessment in an international context* the situation where students are studying remotely at an institution in another country and therefore also need to be evaluated remotely.

In this survey, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions about online assessment based on **your perceptions as student**. Estimated time to answer is 12 minutes.

The survey is structured with 18 questions in 4 parts:

Part A: Factors associated with the experience of online assessment practices

Part B: Attitudes, practices and preferences of online assessment methods

Part C: Contextual and institutional factors

Part D: Profile as student

The survey is completely anonymous, because in no case will identifying data of the participants be collected (names, email addresses or IP addresses of mobile devices), nor will it be possible to deduce the identity of the participants from their answers in the survey.

We greatly appreciate your feedback to design concepts for online assessment and create a course for professional development on this topic, which will result in better teaching and learning processes connected to online assessment in your studies/institution.

If you have any questions about the project or participation in the survey, please send them to [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].

Part A: Factors associated with the experience of online assessment practices

1. How often have you experienced online assessment practices as student during your studies?
(rating scale ranging from 1 to 5: 1. Never, 2 very punctually, 3 in some courses, 4 in most of the courses, 5. Always)
2. In which year/s of study where those courses?
1-2-3-4-5-6 or more
3. Did you have experience with online assessment practices before COVID19?
Yes/No

If yes, please briefly describe this experience. Open textbox.
4. When your instructor(s) presented the information about the online assessment of the course(s), to which degree did you...?
(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3- sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)
 - a. Understand the assessment formats of the course.
 - b. Understand the kind of assessment questions/criteria and grading.
 - c. Understand your rights as students concerning assessment.
 - d. Understand the procedure to review the assessment.
 - e. Have enough time to prepare for the adopted assessment formats.
 - f. Receive support when having technical difficulties.
5. How competent or skilled do you feel about the following digital areas?
(Likert scale 1-5: 1-not at all, 5-very much)
 - a. Information and data access and management.
 - b. Online communication and collaboration.
 - c. Creation of digital contents.
 - d. Safe use of the Internet and technological devices.
 - e. Minor problem solving arising from the use of digital technologies.
6. Considering the infrastructure you have (spaces, devices, connection, etc.), to what extent do you agree with the following statements?
(Likert scale: 1-5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree)
 - a. I have the appropriate spaces (comfortable, without interruptions or interferences...) for online assessment practices.
 - b. I have a good Internet connection for online assessment practices.
 - c. I have technological devices for online assessment practices.
 - d. The technological devices that I have have an appropriate video and audio system for online assessment practices.
 - e. The technological devices that I have are well protected for safe online assessment practices (e.g., antivirus, firewall, etc.).

f. The technological devices that I have have the needed programs (software) for online assessment practices.

Part B: Attitudes, practices and preferences of online assessment methods

7. To what extent you agree with the following statements?

(Likert scale: 1-5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4= agree and 5=strongly agree):

- I like to receive online feedback during my learning process.
- Online assessment requires more time and/or effort than in-class assessment.
- Online assessment is easier than in-class assessment.
- I prefer online assessment to in-class assessment.
- Online assessment contributes more to my learning than in-class assessment.
- Online assessment facilitates originality and creativity.

8. Which types of online assessment practices...

(matrix with the practices to evaluate)

a) have you experienced formative assessment? (during the learning process) (Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3-sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)

b) have you experienced summative assessment? (at the end of the learning process) (Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3- sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)

c) which do you feel more comfortable with? (multiple choice)

Closed-book written exam (written exam without supporting materials (notes, books))

Open-book written exam (written exam with supporting materials (notes, books))

Oral exam Quiz or tests (multiple choice, true/false, etc.)

Portfolio or e-portfolio

Papers/written assignments

Project Presentation (individual or group; poster, exhibitions)

Simulations

Case analysis

Self-assessment

Peer assessment

Others (specify)

9. With which online/digital tools did you realize them... ?

(Likert scale: 1-5, 1-never, 2-rarely, 3-sometimes, 4-very often, 5-always)

LMS task/assignment

LMS questionnaire

LMS forums

Other LMS tools

Videoconference system

Video recording spaces

Video repositories (e.g., Youtube)

Audio recording and repositories (podcast)
External questionnaires (e.g., Kahoot, Socrative)
Online work suites (e.g., Office Word, Google Docs)
Games and/or simulators
Website (e.g., Google Sites, Wix, etc.)
Blog (e.g., Wordpress, Blogger, etc.)
Wiki
Infographics (e.g., easel.ly, Canva)
Digital rubrics and/or checklists
Proctoring software
Safe exam browser
Plagiarism tools (e.g., Turnitin)
Other (specify)

Part C: Contextual and institutional factors

10. Do you consider the infrastructure offered by the institution enough to do online assessment? (e.g. connectivity, spaces, tools offered, etc.)

a) Why (yes/not)? Please explain briefly. (open textbox)

11. How has the pandemic influenced the use of online assessment practices in your studies?

Open textbox.

12. Which opportunities do you see for online assessment in international contexts?

Open textbox.

13. Which challenges do you see for online assessment in international contexts?

Open textbox.

Part D: Profile as student

14. Faculty:

List of faculties according to each university.

15. Discipline that you are studying:

Health & Welfare / Natural Science, Maths & Statistics / Education / Arts & Humanities / Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction / Business, Administration & Law / Social Sciences, Journalism & Information / ICT / Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Veterinary / Other

16. Higher education level where you follow your studies:

Bachelor/Master/Both

17. Year of Study:

Numeric field.

18. Do you combine studies with work?

Yes/No

- a) If yes: Occasional work / Less than 15 hours per week / 15 – 30 hours per week / More than 30 hours per week

Comments, observations... (open text box, voluntary)

If you would like to add something else regarding the questionnaire or the study, please do it so here.

Thank you very much for your participation!

To conclude: if you have a good practice example of online *assessment in an international context* to share, please contact [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].

Administrators' "Survey on Online Assessment in Higher Education"

The Remote.EDU Project (2020-1-DE01-KA226-HE-005782) aims to explore the perceptions of instructors, students and administrators (stakeholders) about online assessment in higher education institutions. The results of this study will serve to draw on the current situation in each of the institutions to consider local, institutional and national perspectives, and will inform the design of concepts for online assessment, the needs for online assessment for virtual mobility and the development of a professional development course for online assessment.

We understand online *assessment, e-assessment or electronic assessment* as a teaching strategy to use technology to assess and evaluate learning goals and acquired competencies, **in any educational modality** (in-class, blended or hybrid learning, online learning) and **moment in the process** (formative e-assessment or assessment for learning during the course of instruction, and summative e-assessment at the end of a course or teaching unit that includes scoring or grading). In addition, we consider *online assessment in an international context* the situation where students are studying remotely at an institution in another country and therefore also need to be evaluated remotely.

In this survey, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions about online assessment based on **your perceptions as administrative staff at your university**. Estimated time to answer is 15 minutes.

The survey is structured with 20 questions in 5 parts:

Part A: Leadership & governance practices

Part B: Teaching & learning assessment support (personal infrastructures)

Part C: Institutional infrastructure

Part D: Contextual factors

Part E: Profile as administrative staff

We greatly appreciate your feedback to design concepts for online assessment and create a course for professional development on this topic, which will result in better support to instructors in relation to online assessment from your side, as administrative staff.

If you have any questions about the project or participation in the survey, please send them to [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].

Part A: Leadership & governance practices

1. To which extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please rate from 1 to 5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree. If you do not know, please select "I do not know".

- Digital learning (and the possibility to do online assessments) is essential for the future of the institution.
- Digital learning and online assessment are part of the mission, vision and global strategy of the institution.
- There is a model of direction and governance regarding digital learning and online assessment.
- There are institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment.
- There are institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment in your faculty / study program(s).
- Learning analytics (data from the learning process and product) are considered strategically by the institution.

2. Do you think the institutional guidelines regarding how to conduct online assessment have been modified/removed/adapted since its development?

Yes/No

- a) Please, explain (open textbox)

3. From your perspective, how does institutional assessment culture and policy influence online assessment practices?

Open textbox

Part B: Teaching & learning assessment support (personal infrastructures)

4. Do you have any relation to the teaching and learning assessment support (instructors or students), with some contact point with online assessment? (e.g., technical support, pedagogical support, etc.)

Yes/No

5. Does the institution have a pedagogical counseling service or infrastructures about online assessment (instructors and/or students)?

Yes/No

- a) If yes, what kind of pedagogical support infrastructure(s) offers the university for online assessment? Please, describe it (material, personal resources).

6. Are instructors offered with professional development courses on online assessment?

Yes/No

a) If yes, what were the specific topics regarding online assessment covered in the courses? (e.g., tools, strategies, etc.) Open textbox

7. Are instructors offered with personal consultation on online assessment?

- a) If yes: pedagogical consultation / technical consultation / both
- b) If yes, which format did they take? (checkboxes, multiple choice) Individual consultation, in small group, online through videoconference, in presence
- c) If yes, what were the specific topics regarding online assessment covered in the consultations? (e.g., tools, strategies, etc.) Open textbox

8. Was this offer of courses enough for the instructors' needs?

Yes/No

a) Please, explain why yes/no. Open textbox.

9. To which extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please rate from 1 to 5, being 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree and 5=strongly agree:

- a) Summative and formative online assessment (S: at the end of the course, and F: during the learning process, respectively) were supported at the same level.
- b) Online self-assessment and peer assessment were supported.
- c) There are institutional guidelines on how to use learning analytics (data from the learning process and product).
- d) The institution uses learning analytics to improve students' learning.
- e) The institution uses learning analytics to optimize instructors' pedagogical strategies.
- f) Quality management and study program design is supported by learning analytics.

Part C: Institutional infrastructure

10. What technical infrastructure offers the university for online assessment? (e.g., connectivity, technological services and devices, etc.)

Open textbox.

11. What are the technological tools that are used for online assessment at the university? (e.g., questionnaires, videoconference systems, etc.)

Open textbox.

12. How do you rate these institutional infrastructures? (Likert 1-5)

- a. Their quantity.
- b. Their quality.
- c. Please, explain your rating. (open textbox)

13. What do you think that are the main difficulties that the institutional infrastructure undergoes in the COVID-19 situation? (e.g., heard from instructors and/or students, read in the institutional press or mailing, etc.)

Open textbox.

14. What do you think that are the main advantages that the institutional infrastructure presents in the COVID-10 situation?

Open textbox.

Part D: Contextual factors

15. From your point of view, how did COVID-19 affect the design, implementation and support of online assessment?

Open textbox.

16. Does your institution already have experience with online assessment in an international context (*where foreign students are studying remotely at your institution and therefore also need to be evaluated remotely*)?

Yes/No/I do not know

- a. Which opportunities do you see for online assessment in international contexts? (open text)
- b. Which challenges do you see for online assessment in international contexts? (open text)

Part E: Profile as administrative staff

17. Current function / main tasks as administrative staff in your institution:

Open textbox.

18. Administrative staff with teaching workload:

Yes/No

19. How familiar are you with the design, implementation, or support of online assessment practices?

(rating scale ranging from 1 to 5: 1 not at all, 5 completely)

If yes, where do you use this knowledge to develop your professional task? (single option)
As part of my role as administrative staff/ Outside my administrative role within the institution (e.g. teaching, research) / Outside my administrative role outside the institution.

Comments, observations... (open text box, voluntary)

If you would like to add something else regarding the questionnaire or the study, please do it so here.

Thank you very much for your participation!

To conclude: if you have a good practice example of *online assessment in an international context* to share, please contact [coordinator of the Remote.EDU project at the partner institution].